

The Agricultural Complex of Yaroslavl Oblast and its Rural Areas: Development Trends and Intra-Regional Differences

Tatyana G. Nefedova¹, Uliana G. Nikolaeva^{1,2}, Tatiana Y. Kondakova^{1,3},
Elena A. Lyzhina¹

1 *Institute of Geography Russian Academy of Sciences, Chief Researcher, Moscow, 119017, Russia*

2 *Institute of Sociology of the Federal Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, 109544, Russia;
Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, 119991, Russia*

3 *Yaroslavl State Pedagogical University named after K.D. Ushinsky, Yaroslavl, 150000, Russia*

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of the research into the current state of agriculture and rural areas of Yaroslavl Oblast, considering specific natural, production, economic and socio-demographic factors. It shows the characteristics and intra-regional differentiation of agricultural production depending on the distance from the region's large cities. The paper shows specific features of rural development in the context of economic contraction, ageing and shrinking of the population, concentration of production and the increasingly significant role of agricultural holdings, as well as the influence of non-productive factors on intra-regional differentiation.

The paper presents statistical calculations by municipal districts and individual enterprises along with the results of socio-geographical expeditions to the rural areas of Yaroslavl Oblast, which included expert interviews with heads of enterprises and local administrations, specialists of various levels, and the population. The mechanisms of development of the agro-industrial complex of the region, the specifics of its current organisation, its challenges, and its impact not only on the food supply for the population, but also on the socio-geographical space and the living conditions of the local population are considered.

Relative proximity to towns or cities, the patterns of use of local resources, participation in government support programmes, the degree of modernisation of production, availability of exclusive products, the staffing and the personnel policies, and personal qualities of the managers were identified as key success factors for agricultural enterprises regardless of their size. Both general and specific current challenges to the development of different types of enterprises in the Non-Black

Soil Zone were identified, including the shrinking of crop acreage and the dependence of livestock farming on fodder grain purchased from southern Russia. Equally important is the acute shortage of labour, the difficulties in recruiting migrant workers, and wage growth without increases in skills and productivity in the face of labour shortages. The consequences of the sanctions include difficulties in purchasing genetic material and vaccines from abroad, and in the renewal and maintenance of imported equipment.

Keywords

Yaroslavl Oblast, rural areas, agriculture, agricultural holdings, concentration of production, labour resources, depopulation, local governance

JEL codes: D10, D21, J11, J21, O18, Q13

Introduction

Incomplete urbanisation is one of the key features of the spatial development of modern Russia, which is partly caused by growing economic centralisation and increasing spatial contrasts, including in living standards, between large cities and the rest of the territory. Despite the weakening and reversal of centripetal population shifts in many foreign countries (Geyer and Kontuly 1993; Fielding 1989), as well as in Russia at the turn of the 21st century (Nefedova and Treyvish 2019), in recent years the role and appeal of large cities [in Russia] have increased, in particular that of Moscow (Druzhinin 2022), which continues to stimulate the depopulation of rural areas (Denisenko and Nikolaeva 2015). This is especially true for the old-cultivated non-black soil regions of the European part of Russia (Old-developed regions 2021). The outflow of the rural population to regional centres and large cities highlights the critical issue of labour resources available in rural areas.

At the same time, the current shift of Russian agricultural production to more southern regions that have favourable natural conditions for agriculture (Nefedova 2019) and the abandonment of land in Russia's Non-Black Soil Zone led to a spatial 'compression' of agriculture (Nefedova 2024) and settlement (Mkrtchyan 2018, 2019) towards the main regional centres, thus strengthening the socio-economic heterogeneity of this territory. The concentration of agricultural production in agricultural holdings (Uzun et al. 2022), the emergence of new technologies in the surviving agricultural enterprises increased the requirements to labour resources in rural areas while significantly reducing employment, which intensified the outflow of the local population. For such areas, a geographical approach to research is particularly important, which makes it possible to identify the intra-regional heterogeneity of socio-economic challenges, including those linked to the transformation of agricultural production.

Yaroslavl Oblast, which borders the Moscow Metropolitan Region from the north, faces many of the socio-economic challenges characteristic of modern Russia, especially its non-black soil regions (Nefedova 2024). This includes problems related to the development of agricultural production, although Yaroslavl Oblast is by no means a predominantly agricultural region. It ranks 50th in Russia in terms of gross agricultural output, ahead only of the Ivanovo, Kostroma, and Smolensk oblasts of the Central Federal District, and reaching just a quarter of that of Moscow Oblast. Even the more northern oblasts, Leningrad and Vologda, have the outputs 2.5 and 1.5 times larger, respectively (Regiony Rossii 2023). Nevertheless,

the region has shown a relatively steady growth in agricultural output in recent years. This was largely due to the advantages of its geographical proximity to Moscow, and it was accompanied by a further concentration of production in large agricultural enterprises, while the share of medium-sized enterprises, individual farmers and household farms declined. At the same time, the regional financial results of both crop and livestock production are significantly inferior to those of the more southern regions and even those of the Moscow and Leningrad Oblasts (Regiony Rossii 2023: 659).

Although agriculture does not play a leading role in the development of the region (7.7% of its gross regional product) (Regiony Rossii 2023: 19), it is important for the food supply of Moscow and other non-black soil regions of Russia, as well as 1.2 million of its own population. Therefore, it is important to understand the mechanisms of development of the agro-industrial complex and its modern specifics, to identify its problems and their impact on food supply and living conditions of the local population.

The problems of rural development and agriculture in Yaroslavl Oblast have been the subject of research both at the end of the Soviet period and during the radical disintegration of Soviet economic mechanisms (Yaroslavl Oblast 1993), as well as in recent years (Averkieva et al. 2021; Voronova et al. 2016; Zholudeva 2019), including by the authors of this paper (Nefedova 2021; Lyzhina 2024; Kondakova and Bragin 2021). The role of Yaroslavl Oblast in the old-cultivated areas was analysed (Old-developed regions 2021), with special attention paid to the shrinking of the developed space in Central Russia and the abandonment of agricultural land, which is characteristic of many regions surrounding Moscow Oblast (Nefedova and Medvedev 2020).

The paper compares municipal districts and individual enterprises to describe the organisation of the Oblast's agro-industrial complex, the losses incurred and the benefits gained as a result of the all-Russian agricultural transformation, and the relationship between its operation and the dynamics and employment of the population. Its main challenges, dependence on geographical location, natural conditions and specialisation of individual districts, its labour potential and other factors are identified.

Materials and methods of research

This research is based on municipal statistics from the early 1990s to 2022–2023, data on agricultural enterprises, and the results of the economic and socio-geographical field-work conducted by the authors in a number of districts of Yaroslavl Oblast in 2024, including interviews with heads of district and village administrations, managers of companies, including those which are part of large agricultural holdings, and the population.

Natural and social differences in the rural areas of Yaroslavl Oblast

Due to its relatively small size, significant differences in natural conditions are not characteristic of the region, except for a slight increase in the sum of active temperatures above 10 degrees Celsius in the south of the region (Pereslavl Urban Okrug and Rostov District). Social contrasts within the Oblast are more pronounced. They are mainly caused by the influence of the regional central city, Yaroslavl, one of the largest cities north of Moscow, with a population of 608.000 as of early 2025, which forms a pronounced suburban zone

in Yaroslavl District with an increased density of the rural population at 35 persons per square kilometre (Nefedova 2024). During the Soviet period of active urbanisation, even the suburban area lost a quarter of its population between 1959 and 1989, but in the post-Soviet period its population increased by 40% between 1989 and 2024. Rybinsk, the Oblast's second largest city with its 177.000 inhabitants, does not form an urban area with a high rural population density (having 8.4 persons per square kilometre), and its population is declining (in 2024 it was 68% of the 1989 level). The relatively short distance between the Oblast's two largest cities (about 80 km) also contributes to this. In general, there is an area of increased rural population density along the M-8 motorway from the borders of Moscow Oblast to the city of Yaroslavl.

The contrasts between Yaroslavl District and the more remote northern districts near Rybinsk Reservoir are particularly stark: Poshekhonsky, Nekouzsky and Breitovsky districts each have rural population densities of 1.2-2.5 persons per square kilometre and show the strongest rural population outflows (Table 1).

Table 1. Size and trends of the rural population and its components in Yaroslavl Oblast according to distance from the regional central city

Order of Neighbourhoods Relative to Oblast Central City	Rural Population Trends, 2023/1990	Migration Balance for 2018-2022			Natural Population Decline for 2018-2022	Migration and Natural Decline per 1.000 Population, for 2018-2022
		Intra-regional	Between regions	International migration		
		%	persons	persons		
1	143.0	6604	2341	131	-1385	112
2	80.5	-891	247	290	-5009	-45
3	72.1	-1428	256	313	-10923	-65
4	65.7	-671	-374	82	-2533	-125

Source: Rosstat data by municipalities. *Notes:* 1 – suburban Yaroslavl District, 2 – municipal districts adjacent to the regional central city, second-order neighbourhoods, 3 and 4 – districts that are third- and fourth-order neighbourhoods

Apart from the differences between suburban and peripheral areas, the neighbourhood with Moscow Oblast has a significant impact on the regional population trends. Pereslavl Urban Okrug and Uglich District, which border on Moscow Oblast, are attractive for migrants from various regions of Russia and countries of the Near Abroad, partly because of the opportunity to find a job in Moscow or Moscow Oblast. On the other hand, this is also an incentive for the working-age local population to move to the capital or its vicinity. The northern districts of the Oblast, furthest from the regional central city, face the most challenging situation, having lost more than 12% of their population in the last five years alone as a result of out-migration and natural population decline. At such a rate of decline, they are at risk of significant depopulation in the next 10-20 years.

The contrasts in the density of the rural population of the Oblast, especially in its southern part, are somewhat blurred in summer when summer residents come to the countryside not only from Yaroslavl or Rybinsk, but also from Moscow and the cities

of the Moscow region (Starikova and Sheludkov 2021). The suburban Yaroslavl District, as well as the southern Pereslavl District, which has effectively become Moscow's suburban dacha zone, have a particularly large number of summer residents, both in allotment associations and in villages. The 2016 agricultural census data and the analysis of the latest space imagery show that the summer residents of allotment associations and the city residents who have bought or inherited country homes in villages are responsible for an average 50% increase in the population of the Yaroslavl and Pereslavl districts during the summer, while in some villages of these districts the increase is 2-4 times, and the Borisoglebsky, Gavrilovsky, and Tutayevsky districts see a 40% increase (Nefedova and Medvedev 2020).

Agriculture in Yaroslavl Oblast

In Yaroslavl Oblast, about two-thirds of the crop acreage has been abandoned over the past 30 years, and the region has lost 78% of its livestock compared with the 1990 level, especially in the northern districts that are further from the centre (Table 2). Nevertheless, the region has managed to significantly renew its agro-industrial complex and remains an important producer of animal products, including for the Moscow metropolitan area. In contrast to Soviet times, the concentration of livestock production has increased due to the creation of large agro-industrial complexes: 74% of the region's livestock and poultry meat and 60% of its eggs are produced in Rybinsk District. Milk production is more dispersed, but 28% of milk is produced by farms in the suburbs of Yaroslavl, and a further 19% and 17% by large livestock complexes in the Borisoglebsky and Rostovsky districts, respectively. It is the agricultural holdings that have become the main drivers of agricultural development in the Oblast.

Table 2. Distribution and trends of agricultural production in Yaroslavl Oblast according to distance from the regional central city

Order of Neighbourhoods Relative to Oblast Central City	Proportion of Crop Acreage in the Oblast in 2022	Crop Acreage Trends, 2022 in % of 1990	Total Livestock in 2022	Including in agricultural organisations, 2022	Livestock Trends, 2022 in % of 1990	Output in 2022, %		
						Cattle and Poultry Meat	Milk	Eggs
	%	%	Thousand head	%	%			
Total Oblast	3.0	36.0	106.1	87.8	21.6	100	100	100
1	7.3	67.5	29.3	96.5	55.7	4.8	27.9	4.6
2	3.4	30.2	29.6	78.7	24.7	7.2	31.1	11.7
3	3.3	37.3	41.9	79.8	13.2	85.4	38.4	75.1
4	1.2	26.3	5.3	70.0	7.1	2.6	2.6	8.6

Source: Rosstat data by municipalities. *Notes:* 1 – suburban Yaroslavl District, 2 – municipal districts adjacent to the regional central city, second-order neighbourhoods, 3 and 4 – districts that are third- and fourth-order neighbourhoods.

By 2023, there were more than a hundred agricultural enterprises of various forms of ownership in Yaroslavl Oblast, including agricultural production co-operatives (APCs), joint-stock companies (JSCs), farm households, etc. In 2022, half of the 40 largest farms with revenues between 100 million roubles and 10 billion roubles were concentrated in just a few districts: apart from the suburbs of Yaroslavl, these were mainly Rybinsk District, Rostov District, and their neighbouring districts (Fig. 1). Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC is one of the strongest agricultural holdings, whose main facility is located in Rybinsk District (Table 3). The revenues of the nearby Volzhanin PJSC, the largest egg producer, are only slightly lower. Among milk producers, Krasnyi Mayak Ltd. stands out; it is located in Rostov District, where several other large and quite successful enterprises are also based.

Figure 1. Firms and their sites in Yaroslavl Oblast. Source: www.testfirm.ru.

Table 3. Twenty largest agribusinesses and their revenues in 2023 in the suburban Yaroslavl District, Rostov District, and Rybinsk District

#	Name (Group)	District of operation	Line of business	Revenue. RUB mln
1	Yaroslavskiy Broiler, JSC	Rybinsk, Tutayev, etc.	Poultry farming, meat production	10257.1
2	Volzhanin PJSC	Rybinsk	Poultry farming, egg production	9020.5
3	Krasnyi Mayak Ltd.	Rostov, Borisoglebsk	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	2923.0
4	Agromir Ltd.	Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	1135.3
5	Rodina, Plemzavod Ltd.	Danilov, Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	908.5
6	Sever, Ptitsefabrika Ltd.	Yaroslavl	Poultry farming	763.2
7	Plemzavod Yaroslavka JSC	Yaroslavl, Tutayev	Mixed farming	606.2
8	Pakhma, Agrofirma CJSC	Yaroslavl, Gavrilov-Yam	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	602.8
9	AGRONERO, Belaya Dacha Ltd.	Rostov	Vegetable farming	366.7
10	Melenkovskiy, Yarmolprod Ltd.	Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	257.6
11	Dzerzhinsky Plemzavod	Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	225.4
12	Tatischevskoye JSC	Rostov	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	213.7
13	Novyy Put' JSC	Rostov	Mixed farming	188.6
14	Arefinskoye, Ramoz Ltd.	Rybinsk	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	181.0
15	Iskra Ltd.	Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	156.3
16	SPK Revolutsiya Ltd.	Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	141.3
17	Niva Ltd.	Rostov	Mixed farming	126.8
18	Druzhba, production agricultural co-operative	Yaroslavl	Cereal farming	102.5
19	Agrotsekh Ltd.	Yaroslavl	Dairy cattle farming, milk production	97.3
20	Mologa, Agri Volga Ltd.	Rybinsk	Mixed farming	95.3

Source: www.testfirm.ru.

The significant concentration of agricultural production near the central cities of the oblasts is a typical picture for the regions of the Non-Black Soil Zone (Old-developed regions 2021: 93-101). The authors of this paper focused on the modern features of firms and household farms outside the suburbs of regional central cities. This explains our choice of Rybinsk District and Rostov District as the main objects of a large-scale study of trends, successes and current problems of the agro-industrial complex of Yaroslavl Oblast. In order to contrast and better understand the problems of other producers, we chose Nekrasovskiy District to the north-east of Yaroslavl District, situated in a hollow between Yaroslavl and the city of Kostroma, and Nekouzskiy District in the north-west of Yaroslavl Oblast, beyond the Volga River, characterised by a significant population decline and abandonment of agricultural land.

Figure 2. Rural population and agro-production trends (crop acreage and livestock) in selected key types of districts of Yaroslavl Oblast according to Rosstat data for 1990 and 2022.

Rostov District: historical context and contemporary developments

Rostov Municipal District has a number of natural advantages over other regions of the Oblast, due not only to its southern location, but also to the features of Lake Nero. As a result of the shrinking water surface of the lake, a wide strip of fertile soils on the lake sludge (saproel) had formed around it, which, even before the 20th century, gave rise to a well-known vegetable growing area, with a dense network of settlements and a special type of peasant farms. They not only supplied vegetables to Moscow and St. Petersburg but also went to set up market gardens in other provinces of Russia (Saushkin 1947). At the end of the 19th century, the density of the rural population in the area exceeded 50 persons per square verst [A square verst is an old Russian unit, approximately equal to 1.14 sq. km. – Translator's note], and near Lake Nero it reached 200 persons per square verst. The villages there looked more like small towns with occasional stone houses. In 2023, the rural population density in the district was 7.6 persons per square kilometre.

Even in the more vibrant, old-developed Rostov District located on the M-8 federal motorway 200 kilometres from Moscow, 50 settlements have no population left, and 76 settlements have fewer than 5 people left. Such heavy losses also affect the quality of human capital; most of those who had any ambition at all have long since left. Retirees dominate in most settlements of the district, while some of the remaining working-age population earn their living in Moscow or Moscow Oblast or Yaroslavl. Villages with fewer than 50 inhabitants have become what are known as dachas, with convenient road connections to both Moscow and Yaroslavl, a nearby lake, and the city of Rostov. Nevertheless, the traditional vegetable growing skills and, in general, the increased agricultural activity of the population have been preserved, which is evident from the numerous stalls selling Rostov onions, vegetables, berries, jams and fish along the motorway that passes through the villages near Lake Nero.

Rostov (official name Rostov Veliky, i.e. Rostov the Great), a small but historically important city of 27,000 inhabitants, is subordinate to the Oblast, although it is the district's central city. Moreover, the Rostov Kremlin, which attracts hundreds of tourists, occupies a significant part of the city and has been actively repaired and restored in recent years, is under the jurisdiction of the federal authorities in Moscow. All this has a negative impact on the budgets of both the city and Rostov District, including their ability to provide the area and settlements outside the main tourist routes with roads, pipeline gas, etc. The tourism industry is composed of privately owned, mostly small hotels, which is in part due to tourists favouring accommodations in Yaroslavl, located just 57 kilometres away.

However, historical traditions and natural conditions have contributed to the development of the modern large agricultural complex in the district, which has distinctive features. Rostov District is characterised by opposite types of business activity. On the one hand, the role of small entrepreneurs has been higher compared to other regions, including in agriculture; their main income comes from their own produce, often sold along the highway from stalls or in small shops. On the other hand, there are large agricultural holdings that have taken the place of former Soviet facilities.

In Soviet times, Rostov District had 25 collective or state farms on its fertile lands. Most of them went bankrupt in the 1990s and 2000s. New people and a lot of money came into agriculture. For example, one of the largest milk producers in the whole of Yaroslavl Oblast, Krasnyi Mayak Ltd. with 3,600 cattle in 2022, was established on the basis of two facilities, including a former large Soviet state farm. It supplies its products to Wimm-Bill-Dann, Ecomilk and other companies, as well as retail chains in and outside central Russia (Lyzhina

2024). The costs of dairy farming are high and pay back in a minimum of 7-8 years, or about 10 years for closed animal husbandry centres. All this requires a variety of markets to sell to, including exporting milk powder, as well as milk processing. The company has around 300 employees. 16,000 hectares of land is used to grow part of the fodder consumed (the rest is imported from southern Russia) and potatoes for sale (a quarter of the potato output of the entire Yaroslavl Oblast). There are also private label shops. There are also four other dairy or mixed speciality farms, which are much smaller but important for employment and food supply, and about 10 household farms with 1 to 5 employees.

Of particular note is the former Soviet state farm Ovoshchevod, which was bought in 2016 by the Moscow-based Belaya Dacha Group, which owns companies in regions from Tatarstan to Krasnodar Krai. In Rostov District, the newly established company Agro-Nero specialises in the cultivation of leafy greens, herbs and alliums. Previously, neither the favourable natural conditions (a temperate climate is better for growing these crops than a more southern, arid climate), nor the land reclamation carried out during Soviet times, nor the vegetable-growing traditions had helped the pre-existing enterprises to survive, until large investments, backed by the parent company, came along with modern machinery and, most importantly, guaranteed sales. The new firm was able to quickly build a solid foundation and now produces 70% of its own raw materials. The company buys the rest from individual farmers, supporting small businesses that are typical of the area. According to the management, 'it took five years to see the first return on investment, and it generally takes a decade to gain solid financial footing.'

Marketing problems, including dependence on retail chains, make the business much more difficult. Retail chains are typically out of reach for small producers. But the main problem for almost all firms is the shortage of personnel, which has worsened in recent years, although the number of employees, for example at Agro-Nero, varies throughout the year (from 150 in summer to 50 in winter). The management and technical staff of large companies are recruited mainly from large cities such as Moscow, Vologda or Yaroslavl. Some middle and lower-level staff also have to be transported from Yaroslavl or recruited from Chuvashia or other Russian regions, as well as from Central Asia. There are problems with housing for the resettled workers. Although there appear to be a large number of abandoned houses in villages scattered throughout the district, their dilapidation, remoteness, and poor infrastructure make them virtually unusable.

Rybinsk District: major firms

Two major firms, Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC (chicken production) and Volzhanin PJSC (egg production), are located relatively close to the city of Rybinsk (13-16 km). Both firms are notable for their huge output, high profits (and, accordingly, taxes paid to the regional and federal budgets), state-of-the-art equipment, efficient management, wide sales geography within the region and far beyond, including abroad. All this makes these firms significant not only at the regional level, but also at the federal level. In terms of production, Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC ranks 18th out of Russia's top 20 poultry meat producers (65,000 tonnes live weight per year), while Volzhanin PJSC was recently ranked second in Russia for annual egg output (1.5 billion).

Both companies have their origins in poultry farms from the late 1970s and early 1980s when it was decided to establish small-scale production facilities in every oblast and almost every district as part of the USSR's programme to provide eggs and poultry meat to the pop-

ulation. These industry giants are rare examples of a very successful market transformation of Soviet poultry producers.

Located close to the city of Rybinsk (population 198,000), these firms can take advantage of the well-developed suburban infrastructure and employ not only local residents but also skilled workers from Rybinsk or the relatively nearby town of Tutayev (about 40 km) and even Yaroslavl (about 80 km).

Neither of the two firms received the best inheritance from the Soviet period, including a sizeable proportion of wetlands. In the decades of post-Soviet transformation, they have significantly expanded their territories (by buying bankrupt neighbouring state or collective farms), built new buildings and storage facilities, launched new production lines, fully modernised production, and increased output. Volzhanin PJSC, for example, has increased its output by 8–10 times over the last twenty years, while reducing its energy consumption and input requirements (water, heat, etc.) by 3–4 times.

It is characteristic of both firms that they have moved to the latest poultry and egg production technologies, with the purchase of imported highly productive crossbred chickens bred for meat or egg production. They have completely renewed their machinery with the purchase of European or American equipment for microclimate maintenance, feeding, egg collection and grading, non-contact killing and poultry dressing.

The key success factor for Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC was the establishment of a Russian American joint venture in 1996, through the patronage and connections of top officials of Yaroslavl Oblast. Immediately the transition to highly productive meat breeds (a UK-developed crossbreed Arbor Acres) was carried out, a modern technology of chicken breeding was implemented, and new compound feeds were introduced, which the Rybinsk compound feed plant started to produce. However, the drive of the first stage of modernisation was not sufficient, and in 2007 the firm faced a crisis, as production decreased, wages were delayed, and production capacity was partially frozen. The company regained momentum with the arrival of a new team of managers and owners, who had a good economic and managerial background from their experiences in Moscow, good connections in Moscow, and high qualifications. The new management were able to get the company included in government support programmes for the industry, which secured loans in the amount of approximately 750 million roubles, a huge amount at the time, and enabled to purchase state-of-the-art imported machinery. In 2021, they built their own compound feed factory, along with huge modern granaries, and production continues to increase (for example, another new poultry facility with a capacity of 500,000 birds was launched in 2024).

The history of Volzhanin PJSC was somewhat different, although the results of the two companies are similar. In 1996, when the original Soviet-era company was in deep crisis, a staff veterinarian, L. Yu. Kosteva was elected general director. Having studied modern management and taken part in executive training and development trips to market leaders abroad, she started an active modernisation programme, focusing on imported technologies for breeding highly productive cross-bred egg-laying chickens. The company also participated in major government support programmes. The loans and grants it received allowed it to renew its machinery and fully automate production (including egg collection and grading) using imported equipment from the world's leading manufacturers. In recent years, the company has also started high-tech production of egg mixes, dried egg products and sports nutrition based on chicken protein.

One of the main problems that both major market players face in relation to the natural characteristics of the region is the inadequacy of their own feed base – locally grown cereals

and grasses are only a supplement to the main grain feed and nutritious mixes purchased from southern Russia. Nevertheless, they are trying to expand their areas of grass and cereal production to maintain a degree of resilience to annual fluctuations in grain prices and are even making efforts to reclaim some of the overgrown fields, although this is proving very costly and inefficient for the area. Both companies have built modern grain storage facilities and feed mills for long-term storage and complete disinfestation of purchased grain.

The lower profitability of poultry farming in the natural conditions of the Non-Black Soil Zone compared to southern Russia is compensated by their focus on high quality standards (for example, Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC was one of the first companies [in Russia] to complete product quality certification to supply chicken meat to McDonald's and is now certified to produce halal meat). They have also entered some foreign markets, in particular selling chicken meat and feet to China. Entering foreign markets with their egg products is still limited due to a high capacity of the Russian market and a higher profitability of domestic sales.

In recent years, however, the sanctions have forced the company management to address the difficult tasks of sourcing hatching eggs and day-old chicks of highly productive imported breeds (without genetic renewal, the productivity of subsequent generations of chickens decreases sharply) and imported vaccines adapted to these breeds (Russian development in this area is still at the experimental stage, and production of poultry vaccines that meet the market needs has not reached a commercial scale), as well as repair and maintenance of sophisticated imported automated equipment. International training programmes for engineers conducted in partnership with equipment manufacturers have been frozen, and only on-line consulting has been maintained. A partial switch to Russian or Chinese analogues that the companies are aiming for is a difficult and rather slow process.

Labour shortages are a common problem for all large companies. While in the early and mid-2000s, according to their management, there was still an adequate and, in some cases, even an excessive number of employees available, in the last decade many specialists have retired and in general the local population is shrinking and ageing rapidly (Denisenko and Nikolaeva 2015). Even with higher salaries and a good benefits package, it is difficult to recruit or retain young people, as they are much more attracted to an office job in a big city. This is despite the fact that in both companies all processes are mechanised wherever possible, they have their own canteens, run social programmes (for example, Volzhanin PJSC even owns a medical and sports centre and in some cases pays for medical treatment for employees).

Highly qualified engineers and technicians are especially scarce, as well as veterinarians with modern training and experienced zootechnicians. Many veterinary schools were closed in the post-Soviet period, and even the nearest State Agricultural Academy in Yaroslavl does not train basic veterinarians. There is a particular shortage of highly skilled poultry workers who would be poached from farm to farm and sought after in other regions, and the companies are paying for training in modern technologies.

Despite steadily rising wage costs and an active recruitment policy, the poultry companies are struggling to compete for labour, especially engineering personnel, with the military-industrial complex, which has expanded in the cities in recent years. Rising wages have become the main item of expenditure for both companies. Their cost structures have changed dramatically over the last 15 years: wages have risen seven-fold, energy and feed prices have risen 3.6-3.8 times and the price for their meat products has tripled. As a result, the profitability of production, which used to reach 17-20% in the mid and late 2010s, has fallen to almost 8-13% in the early 2020s, and this indicator has reached its full improvement

potential. These levels of profitability are not as high as they may appear, given that the companies incur significant additional expenses for regional charitable programmes, transfer funds to support the Special Military Operation, and incur other non-production expenses.

The businesses increasingly have to rely on migrant workers (mostly Uzbeks, as is the case in the region), who, for example, make up about 10% of the workforce at Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC. A company dormitory was built for temporary workers, and daily meals are provided. For those with limited Russian language skills, signs with instructions in their native language are posted in all production areas. However, there are still labour shortages and difficulties in obtaining work permits and other necessary documents for foreign workers from Central Asia; the need to recruit migrants from outside the former USSR (particularly from Vietnam) for unskilled jobs has been the subject of debate.

The decline in the local employable population means that not only Yaroslavskiy Broiler JSC and Volzhanin PJSC, but all firms in Rybinsk District and neighbouring districts are facing rather tough competition for labour resources. In the neighbouring Tutayevsky District, a giant export-oriented ice cream factory Icebery was launched in 2021, and there is a plan to set up a free economic zone in the district's central small town of Tutayev, which dramatically intensifies the competition for workers in the region.

Nekrasovsky District – how can medium-sized agribusinesses survive?

In Nekrasovsky District, which is lost in the forest between the suburbs of Yaroslavl and Kostroma, agriculture has not fared well. The lure of the big cities is particularly strong here, and the federal highway linking the regional centres, which runs through the district, ensures the possibility of daily commuting to these cities or areas close to them. Compared with 1990, the district has retained only 20% of its crop acreage and 10% of its livestock (Fig. 1, Table 2). Even the local residents have almost no livestock left in their backyards.

Let us consider the main problems of the agricultural complex using the example of a medium-sized farm (1200 head of cattle) with 60 employees, which has survived from the Soviet period, although at that time it employed 450. The farm is situated closer to Yaroslavl, which allows the owner, a young man from Yaroslavl with a degree in finance and perhaps in another field from a Moscow university, who acquired the business with the help of his relatives, to live in the city and commute to work every day. However, he wanted not only to save the farm and make a profit, but also to make life more exciting for the employees and local residents. He is the only one in the neighbourhood trying to maintain and develop cattle farming, despite the fact that all the premises are old Soviet legacy. With a milk yield of 9.5 tonnes per cow per year and production costs of 30 roubles per litre in 2024, he was able to sell milk in Moscow for 43 roubles per litre, plus 1 rouble in non-repayable subsidies from the government. But this was not enough to develop production rapidly. It was not until the sixth year of operation that any real profit was made, before which all income was used to pay off debts and buy and replace equipment. Cattle are not put out to pasture to prevent a drop in milk production. Fodder has to be purchased, although, according to the manager, if there were machines and storage equipment available, it would be possible to grow some fodder within the oblast: not all the abandoned lands had overgrown with forest. Moreover, growing plants allows for a quick return on investment. So, there are still people interested in farming, but government support for them is clearly inadequate. The main problem for small and medium-sized livestock farmers is that their herds are too small to qualify for

large-scale government programmes of low-interest loans and subsidies. Meanwhile, there is very little co-operation between individual farmers and small and medium-sized agricultural firms to defend their interests at regional and federal level and attempts to set up an association of local producers have so far stalled at the initial stage.

Cattle producers have some advantage over poultry producers in the current environment, i.e., a relatively lower dependence on imported genetic material, although the need for imported vaccines remains. However, the main problem identified by other managers is the same – the shortage of working-age men, especially young men, in rural areas, which dramatically increases the dependence on migrant labour.

Nekouzsky District: Agriculture, a dying sector – what comes next?

Nekouzsky District in the north-west of Yaroslavl Oblast is the successor of the Mologa region, although the museum of the former town of Mologa, which was submerged by the waters of Rybinsk Reservoir, is located in Rybinsk. Despite this, the district is home to many migrants from the flooded areas, who still call themselves Mologans. The construction of the Rybinsk waterworks began in 1935. In 1939, the current Nekouzsky District had 51,000 inhabitants living in more than 300 settlements. By 1959 the population had shrunk to 42,000, by 1989 to 23,000, and by 2022 to 12,000. Until the mid-1990s, in addition to the district centre, there were industrial enterprises under the authority of the Federal Penitentiary Service in two urban-type settlements. The largest settlement is Oktyabr, where a peat extraction plant closed in 2016. A molecular sieve factory in the settlement of Volga is still in operation. In Novy Nekouz, the district's central settlement with a population of 3,200, only social services and small businesses remain.

It should also be noted that the district is cut off from more vibrant places by the Volga River and the Reservoir. Despite its relative proximity to Rybinsk, there is no bridge on the direct route, only a ferry that operates infrequently. The only reliable way to cross the Volga is much further south, near the town of Uglich, which would more than double the length of the journey from Rybinsk.

This isolation from active life and the general demographic and economic decline are most evident in agriculture. Flax cultivation, which was characteristic of these northern districts of the oblast, disappeared five years ago, whereas in Soviet times there were two flax mills in operation, although they were heavily subsidised by the government. The cost of producing flax here is high, while the quality, and therefore the price, is rather low.

The cost of grain is also higher here than in other districts, which is why collective farms were only able to survive here in Soviet times with large subsidies. In the last two decades, the crop acreage has shrunk from 40,000 to 8,000 hectares. Small factories that processed milk into cheese and butter have also closed. There is now one farm in the district with 380 head of cattle and 40 employees and several smaller farms. The crop acreage is shrinking, as locally produced grain is more expensive than grain purchased from southern Russia. The main problem, however, is still the marketing: small farms struggle to secure shelf space in retail chains. There are also a few individual farmers in the district, with 5 to 10 cattle each, who started their business with the help of subsidies received in the early 2010s. They sell milk and dairy products to the local population and summer residents.

The main concern of the district administration is to find investors, any investors, for these vacant, partly waterlogged lands covered with unproductive forest. In principle, it is possible to keep beef cattle here at low cost, with summer grazing and overseeding of pas-

tures. But the district has a limitation: it is only possible to graze cattle comfortably for six weeks in a year. Farms are switching to year-round zero grazing, although milk yields are not high: the Yaroslavl breed yields 3–4 tonnes of milk a year, its Holstein cross up to 7 tonnes a year. Given the decline of agribusiness and the distance from more vibrant economic centres, the proportion of small farms owned by the local population is higher (Fig. 1). However, most of the land is not in demand by either businesses or the population and is therefore not legally subdivided into land ownership units. This leaves the district short of income.

A combination of agriculture and forestry, which is the basis of many agribusinesses in neighbouring Vologda and Kostroma oblasts (Averkieva 2017), is also limited here due to the relatively low quality of wetland forests. Peat remains the main, but still insufficiently demanded, resource of the district, although the enterprise in the settlement of Oktyabr went bankrupt due to a lack of demand for peat as a fuel. However, peat is also a valuable fertiliser, including for greenhouses. However, no investors have yet been found for peat extraction.

As leading industries shrink, so do social assets. Rural settlements are being merged. A hospital in Nizhny Nekouz will be an inter-municipal hospital shared with the town of Uglich, 60 kilometres away. But the district administration is not discouraged, believing that what can be done must be done now – there is a time for everything. Especially as the district has a rich history and a specific culture and rural architecture of the houses of the Sitskari [a historical population in Yaroslavl Oblast of mixed Slavic and Finno-Ugric ancestry – Translator's note], who have lived here since the 13th century. The recreational potential of the reservoir banks, which are gradually being developed by summer residents, is also considerable. There is also a scientific potential – in the village of Borok, on the reservoir bank, almost 300 researchers work in two institutes of the Russian Academy of Sciences. There are five museums that attract tourists, including those travelling along the Volga.

Conclusion

A research of the districts of Yaroslavl Oblast, based among other things on interviews with the managers of enterprises of various sizes, individual farmers and the population, shows that in the relatively difficult natural and social conditions of Russia's Near North regions, with the fragmentation of the land and the dwindling rural population, numerous small and even medium-sized firms do not generate a sufficient and sustainable margin from agriculture. Viable businesses include relatively large companies with substantial investments, a few small firms run by highly motivated people, and those who try to supplement their agricultural business, often run by inertia, with other lines of business, such as timber processing, tourism, and hotel business, etc. The situation is complicated by the sanctions imposed after 2022, which hamper the herd renewal and flock replacement, and repair and maintenance of equipment in large enterprises, etc. Under the new circumstances, the government started to grant subsidies and partially compensate the interest on loans, but only selectively for certain large companies. However, not everything in agriculture depends on the amount of capital and natural conditions. The role of the management and the staff remains high enough to build competitive production even in difficult conditions.

In the 2000s and 2010s, the areas of Yaroslavl Oblast with relatively favourable natural conditions for agriculture underwent a clear process of asset redistribution. Large agricultural firms and non-agricultural corporations bought some bankrupt but relatively promis-

ing former Soviet collective or state farms with a view to modernising them to produce and supply food to the nearest large consumer markets in central and northwestern Russia. The most attractive factors for large agribusinesses are proximity to major highways and relatively short distances to major cities, the key consumers of food. And the main constraint is not so much the natural conditions of the Non-Black Soil Zone as the availability of human capital. Reliability of the staff and their willingness to work in agriculture are the crucial factors.

With increasing labour shortages and the concentration of large agricultural enterprises, the launching of new industrial giants or the establishment of special economic zones with preferential conditions greatly increases competition for local labour and reduces the profitability and sustainability of existing firms. Modern technologies require qualified and self-disciplined staff. There is a particular shortage of mechanics, veterinarians, zootechnicians and engineers who are competent to operate sophisticated imported equipment. Such specialists would be even sought in other regions and poached from other companies. Almost every manager interviewed said that they were short of 'workers'. As a result, workers from other regions of Russia or from Central Asia are recruited for unskilled jobs, which requires addressing additional problems such as obtaining permits and registering foreign citizens, building housing, most often company dormitories, and building the necessary infrastructure.

Given the abundance of abandoned agricultural land, the lack of legal subdivision into former collective farm workers' individual ownership units often makes it impossible to use the land for other purposes. On the other hand, the government has actively encouraged and even partially financed the reclamation of previously abandoned land, which is now covered with secondary forests and bushes¹. In remote areas, however, this process is technically challenging, time-consuming, costly, and largely unprofitable due to the diminished fertility of previously forested soils and the necessity for substantial fertiliser application.

Finally, all the interviewed managers of large, medium or small enterprises in both relatively successful and depressed districts pointed to excessive centralisation (and bureaucracy), which restricts opportunities and bottom-up initiatives, combined with incompetence and, not infrequently, corruption of officials, as the main factors hindering the development of agricultural production.

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Information about the authors

- Tatyana Grigorievna Nefedova – Doctor of Geography (D.Sc.), Chief Researcher. Department of Social and Economical Geography, Institute of Geography Russian Academy of Sciences. Moscow, 119017, Russia. E-mail: trene12@yandex.ru
- Uliana Gennadyevna Nikolaeva – Doctor of Economics, Chief Researcher. Institute of Sociology of the Federal Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Moscow, 109544, Russia; Senior Researcher. Institute of Geography of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Moscow, 119017, Russia; Senior Researcher at the Department of Population. Faculty of Economics, Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 119991, Russia. E-mail: ynikolaeva@list.ru
- Tatiana Yurievna Kondakova – Candidate of Geographical Sciences, Associate Professor; Senior Researcher at the Department of Socio-Economic Geography, Institute of Geography of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Moscow, 119017, Russia; Head of the Department of Socio-Economic Geography and Tourism Yaroslavl State Pedagogical University named after K.D. Ushinsky. Yaroslavl, 150000, Russia. E-mail: tanjakond7@mail.ru.
- Elena Aleksandrovna Lyzhina – Researcher, Institute of Geography of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Moscow, 119017, Russia. E-mail: helen.lyzhina@gmail.com